

Gros Ventre

also known as “Atsina”, “A'ani”

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

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Entry tags: Native American (North American) Religions, Religious Group

The Gros Ventre are native to the plains of North America. The name “Gros Ventre” is a French interpretation of their sign language, and translates to “large belly”. This Algonkian-speaking, historically nomadic people refer to themselves as A'ani, meaning “white-Clay People”, and are also known by the Blackfoot name Atsina. In the late 1880's the Gros Ventre, along with the Assiniboin, were relocated to Fort Belknap Reservation in northern Montana. This entry focuses around the time of 1835-1885, with tribal territory centering around the Milk River, and the Belknap Reservation representing a small portion of Gros Ventre held land. Principal ethnographic authorities use fieldwork, informant accounts, and primary documents to reconstruct Gros Ventre life prior to 1885, which marked the end of the buffalo era and the beginning of consistent missionary contact. The Gros Ventre were traditionally comprised of about 12 bands, each led by a respective chief who was distinguished in war and recognized as the band's leader. Each band also had a Flat Pipe and a Feathered Pipe Keeper, both of whom served as religious leaders while also possessing political influence. The bands would periodically come together as a tribal unit, which was led by a tribal leader. Ceremonial organization cut across band organization, and most religious ceremonies were held at the tribal level. Gros Ventre political and religious life were interwoven, and this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society at large. Gros Ventre religious beliefs included a Supreme Being, who was considered to be the ultimate ruler and controller of all other supernatural beings, as well as the Earth and its inhabitants. The Supreme Being ranked highest in importance; he was always invoked first and received first offerings. Also present in the supernatural realm were ghosts and ancestral spirit helpers, as well as other non-human supernatural beings like Bha'a, the storm ruler or the thunderbird.

Date Range: 1835 CE - 1885 CE

Region: Fort Belknap Reservation and Gros Ventre lands

Region tags: North America, United States of America

This entry focuses around the Gros Ventre living in Fort Belknap Reservation, Montana, USA, around the time of 1880. The specific time focus is 1835-1885, during which tribal territory centered around the Milk River; the reservation represents a small portion of Gros Ventre-held land (see Flannery, 1953:25).

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: Cross-cultural codes 4. *Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.
- Source 3: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-Cultural Codes 3. *Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-295.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=nq13-002>
- Source 1 Description: Flannery, Regina. "Gros Ventres Of Montana: Part 1, Social Life." Catholic University Of America. *Anthropological Series*, no. no. 15, Catholic University of America Press, 1953, pp. xiv, 221.
- Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=nq13-003>
- Source 2 Description: Cooper, John M. (John Montgomery), and Regina Flannery. "Gros Ventres Of Montana: Part 2, Religion And Ritual." Catholic University Of America. *Anthropological Series*, no. no. 16, Catholic University of America Press, 1957, pp. x, 491.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "While the Gros Ventres have been known in our literature since 1751, their contacts with the whites before the middle of the last century were relatively slight. They met traders and trappers and an occasional intermarriage with whites occurred, but active missionary work among the Gros Ventres did not begin until 1884" (Copper and Flannery, 1957:8).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1649 (Frequency of Internal Warfare, resolved rating), indicates that internal warfare seems to be absent or rare. Additionally, SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, indicates that the Gros Ventre are not pacified for all or part of the twenty-five-year time period, as indicated by the ethnographer. Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004.

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (Resolved Rating) originally coded the Gros Ventre as a 3.25, which is between the original code of 3 (external warfare seems to occur at least once every two years), and the original code of 4 (external warfare seems to

occur every year, but usually only during a particular season. Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: The religious group is coterminous with the society at large. Besides being born into a particular family, there is no system for assigning religious affiliation.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that the Gros Ventre would actively recruit new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: "In general, religious and political life were closely interwoven in the Gros Ventre theocracy" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:68).

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Notes: Religious infrastructure is not present. "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972; Column 6: Large or Impressive Structures).

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: See question below for more details.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

Notes: "The keepers were men of eminence, by virtue of their personal qualities and achievements as well as of their office. In view of these and other facts, it is to be expected that the keeper of the Flat Pipe played a role in Gros Ventre political life...When camp was to be moved, the decision as to time and destination was mainly in the hands of the head men, although the keeper would participate...The keeper could be invited to sit in important council meetings, and to participate in elections and in decisions involving policy or action and had a certain veto prerogative thereon. He could, on occasions at least, intercede with considerable power, to resolve conflicts and avert bloodshed. He could accompany war parties and might even have a voice in strategy and tactics, but he was not ex officio a fighter or war-leader. He could, as previously mentioned, afford asylum in his lodge to criminals. All in all, he wielded very considerable influence in the political life of his people, but he was in no sense a dictator" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:68-69).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of apostasy.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 970

Notes: "The Gros Ventres population—always small, relative to that of surrounding tribes—was steadily declining. Hayden's estimate of 1853 placed the total at 2520. In 1883, at the time of the disappearance of the buffalo, the population was officially recorded as being 970. By 1895 it had been reduced to 596" (Flannery, 1953:23).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Religious leaders include the Flat Pipe Keeper and the Feathered Pipe Keeper. "The Flat Pipe was ordinarily in the custody of an official keeper called *nātcā:ta'* (*nātcā*, chief) with his head wife as co-keeper, *nā:tcīθä* (chief woman) and one of their young children as pipe child, *nātc(ə)ta:niθ(ə)*" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:33).

Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: "The keeper and co-keeper were by virtue of their office 'holy' persons, that is, endowed with supernatural powers. Some of these powers were related directly to their main task as custodians of the Pipe, leaders in its ritual, and intercessors with the supernatural world, and will be described under the ritual of the Pipe. Others were conferred on them at or subsequent to the transfer rite, partly to enable them to command the respect due them, partly to give them supernatural efficiency for their own or their people's advantage,—the former being mostly powers to harm, the latter mostly powers to help" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:60).

Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a belief in reincarnation among the Gros Ventre.

Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– Yes

Notes: (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:60)

Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:60)

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: "In olden times before the coming of the whites according to the tradition as handed down to The Boy and Thick, the Flat Pipe was hereditary in one of the families or bands—which one is unknown. The man and wife chosen, from within the family or band, to be keeper and co-keeper were usually a couple in the prime of life, not an old man married to a young woman or an old woman married to a very young man. A couple in the prime of life were chosen so that, even though they already had children, they could still have more. For it was the tribal law that they should designate out of their children, a boy or girl, born after they had entered upon their keepership to remain with them and to succeed to the keepership should both the keeper and his wife die by accident or sickness...In historic times, that is, as far back as definite tribal memory goes, non-hereditary succession has prevailed. It took two forms, elective and volunteer. In the first case, the initiative was taken by others than the prospective keeper; in the second, by the prospective keeper himself" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:33).

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– I don't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of scripture among the Gros Ventre.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972; Column 6: Large or Impressive Structures).

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "At death the souls of all except murderers went to the same spirit habitat, not to the Supreme Being" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:7).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "At death the souls of all except murderers went to the same spirit habitat, not to the Supreme Being" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:7).

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic details.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a belief in reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "Before finally disposing of the body 'something very expensive,' like a big silk handkerchief, was placed over the face. The whole body, including the head, was then wrapped securely in a blanket or robe and tied 'like a mummy.' The body was placed on a stretcher and put in a forked tree, if practicable, the head to the setting sun. Otherwise the corpse might be laid on a knoll and a structure like a sweatlodge built over it to protect it from the wild beasts; or it might be laid in the cleft of a cliff and covered with rocks. For a particularly prominent man, however, his own lodge might serve as his last resting place" (Flannery, 1953:201).

Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cremation.

Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "Only in relatively recent times has burial in the ground been common" (Flannery, 1953:202).

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified.

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified.

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified.

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified.

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of exposing corpses to the elements.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1850, Secondary Bone/Body Treatment: Original Scale, indicates that secondary bone/body treatment does not occur (Schroeder, 2001; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: Placed in trees, on rocks, or in caves

Notes: "Before finally disposing of the body 'something very expensive,' like a big silk handkerchief, was placed over the face. The whole body, including the head, was then wrapped securely in a blanket or robe and tied 'like a mummy.' The body was placed on a stretcher and put in a forked tree, if practicable, the head to the setting sun. Otherwise the corpse might be laid on a knoll and a structure like a sweatlodge built over it to protect it from the wild beasts; or it might be laid in the cleft of a cliff and covered with rocks. For a particularly prominent man, however, his own lodge might serve as his last resting place" (Flannery, 1953:201).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: "It was customary, prior to the time that the Gros Ventres settled down, to place some of the personal belongings of the deceased with the body. When a beloved son died, for instance, his favorite horse might be taken along and killed at the place where the body was laid away" (Flannery, 1953:202).

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifices.

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: "It was customary, prior to the time that the Gros Ventres settled down, to place some of the personal belongings of the deceased with the body. When a beloved son died, for instance, his favorite horse might be taken along and killed at the place where the body was laid away" (Flannery, 1953:202).

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: "It was customary, prior to the time that the Gros Ventres settled down, to place some of the personal belongings of the deceased with the body" (Flannery, 1953:202).

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: "It was customary, prior to the time that the Gros Ventres settled down, to place some of

the personal belongings of the deceased with the body" (Flannery, 1953:202).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Flannery (1953:202) indicate that ground burials were only common in recent times. Traditionally, the deceased would be placed in high trees/rocks, or in a cave.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cenotaphs.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of tomb-crypts.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: "For a particularly prominent man, however, his own lodge might serve as his last resting place. In that case holes would be dug in which the lodge-poles were placed, in order that the structure would be more permanent. The body was laid in the lodge amidst rich furnishings. The ears of the lodge were closed, the cover pegged down, and the whole secured as well as possible" (Flannery, 1953:201).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The Gros Ventre supernatural realm includes a supreme high god (known as the Supreme Being), ghosts/ancestral spirit helpers, and a variety of other non-human supernatural beings. See questions below for more details.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: "The Supreme Being was alone and one, and, as compared with other sacred or superhuman beings of religion, myth, and folklore, he ranked first" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:4).

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: "The Supreme Being resides up above but he is in no sense identified with the sky or firmament or with any heavenly body...While he resided up above, he could be prayed to from anywhere. In this sense he was not localized, whereas many other beings such as power-bestowing ones, were sought out in their particular dwelling places and there prayed to" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:5).

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence describing the Supreme Being as chthonic.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Gros Ventre.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Gros Ventre.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: "Children were taught that the Supreme Being looked down on them from above and saw and heard all that they did, both good deeds such as charity to the needy, and evil ones such as stealing, even when the children thought they were quite alone and unobserved" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:5).

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: "The Supreme Being was emphatically the owner and master of all things, of the universe, the supernatural beings, as above stated, human beings (not merely the Gros Ventres), the animals, the earth, the heavenly bodies. All informants fully agreed on this. As The Boy [informant] reasoned it out: 'He was master of everything on the earth and above, even of the spirit world, and not merely of the Gros Ventres, but of everybody.'" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:5).

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: Cooper and Flannery, 1957:5

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Cooper and Flannery, 1957:5

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "The Supreme Being was actively interested in the welfare of human beings, first of all as the giver, protector and master of life, and as the donor of food, but also as the source of supernatural power and of wealth" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:5).

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: "Equally active was his interest in man's moral and social behavior. He was pleased at such moral or social acts as respect and help to the aged and care of the orphans, and was offended by grave breaches of the moral or social order. He bestowed reward and punishment for such human behavior exclusively or almost exclusively in this life. At death the souls of all except murderers went to the same spirit habitat, not to the Supreme Being" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:7-8).

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: "Equally active was his interest in man's moral and social behavior. He was pleased at such moral or social acts as respect and help to the aged and care of the orphans, and was offended by grave breaches of the moral or social order. He bestowed reward and punishment for such human behavior exclusively or almost exclusively in this life. At death the souls of all except murderers went to the same spirit habitat, not to the Supreme Being" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:7-8).

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "The Supreme Being as the one who 'owns everything' was the provider of food...But all good things to eat, including 'wild' food such as berries, fruits, roots and tubers, came from the Supreme Being and were given by him" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:6).

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– I don't know

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: "The Supreme Being was alone and one, and, as compared with other sacred or superhuman beings of religion, myth, and folklore, he ranked first. Where prayers included invocation of more beings than one, the Supreme Being's name always came first; in ritual invitations before sweating or partaking of food, he was always invited first" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:4).

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: "The Supreme Being also imparted knowledge and warnings to human beings through dreams and through his messenger, the crow" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:7).

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Gros Ventre.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Ghosts were called tsë :k. Another name for ghosts was byi'te:' a word that 'gives the impression like a hollow-eyed bleached-out skull.' An occasional ancestral ghost became the guardian helper of a surviving relative. Gambling power might also be gotten from a ghost. Most ghosts were in their own future abode and did not have any contact at all with the living" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:23). "The ancestral or ghost helper was called tsätsuwa'a, of uncertain etymology. The word was used exclusively for such ancestral helpers, as distinct from other ghosts" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:258).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that human spirits can be seen.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for human spirits having deliberate causal efficacy in the world. In fact, the majority of ghosts do not have contact with the living (see Cooper and Flannery, 1957:23).

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Ghosts of those who had committed unjustified murder, as defined by the Gros Ventre code, did not go where the other souls went, but stayed where their bodies lay or wandered around and 'bothered' the living. If a person suffered a stroke, a ghost, apparently of a murderer, was thought to have caused it and to have twisted the victim's face or mouth and pulled the eyelid down" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:23).

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: "While the survivor was still in deep sleep or trance, he or she—women as well as men could have a ghost helper—would be taught by the ancestral spirit the proper rites, including always and particularly a song, to be used by the survivor in summoning and making use of the spirit" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:259).

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: "While the survivor was still in deep sleep or trance, he or she—women as well as men could have a ghost helper—would be taught by the ancestral spirit the proper rites, including always and particularly a song, to be used by the survivor in summoning and making use of the spirit" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:259).

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Cooper and Flannery, 1957:259

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Gros Ventre.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Next to the Supreme Being, the supernatural being most frequently mentioned by our informants was Bha'a, the storm ruler or the thunderbird" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:9). "The water monster,—or monsters as there appear to be a number of them, for they are reported from various large rivers, and springs where they bathe,—is usually envisioned as a huge, long, more or less serpent-shaped, being with pointed snout and tail, and with a horn or two horns in its forehead. It lives in its lodge under water, is occasionally seen, snatches bathers or swimmers, and carries them down to its underwater dwelling. Drowned persons are supposed to go to or to be captured and held by the water monster in the after-life" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:12-13).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "According to The Boy[informant]: 'Bha'a has control of lightning and thunder, rules it, and releases it at will. He controls it, he is a sort of general manager; some one still higher controls Bha'a. While Bha'a rules the storm, he does so by a sort of delegated power; he has not the power himself' (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:11)."

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "Much, though not all sickness was ascribed to a malevolent being called Atsa..." (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:28).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The Gros Ventre have a variety of supernatural beings including the Supreme Being, ghosts/ancestral helper spirits, and other non-human supernatural beings. It does not appear that these beings are organized into a pantheon-type system. (See Cooper and Flannery, 1957, Chapter 1 Supernatural Beings)

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: "Children were taught that the Supreme Being looked down on them from above and saw and heard all that they did, both good deeds such as charity to the needy, and evil ones such as stealing, even when the children thought they were quite alone and unobserved" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:5).

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: "Equally active was his [the Supreme Being's] interest in man's moral and social behavior. He was pleased at such moral or social acts as respect and help to the aged and care of the orphans, and was offended by grave breaches of the moral or social order. He bestowed reward and punishment for such human behavior exclusively or almost exclusively in this life. At death the souls of all except murderers went to the same spirit habitat, not to the Supreme Being" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:7-8).

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: "Sometimes supernaturally caused ailments followed automatically from the breach of taboos, others were inflicted intentionally by non-human or by human agents" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:310).

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: "Equally active was his [the Supreme Being's] interest in man's moral and social behavior. He was pleased at such moral or social acts as respect and help to the aged and care of the orphans, and was offended by grave breaches of the moral or social order. He bestowed reward and punishment for such human behavior exclusively or almost exclusively in this life. At death the souls of all except murderers went to the same spirit habitat, not to the Supreme Being" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:7-8).

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: "A considerable number of misdeeds, like theft or failure to observe the rules in ceremonial life, were believed to result automatically in supernatural punishment..." (Flannery, 1953:43).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: "Equally active was his [the Supreme Being's] interest in man's moral and social behavior. He

was pleased at such moral or social acts as respect and help to the aged and care of the orphans, and was offended by grave breaches of the moral or social order. He bestowed reward and punishment for such human behavior exclusively or almost exclusively in this life. At death the souls of all except murderers went to the same spirit habitat, not to the Supreme Being" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:7-8).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more details on the agents of supernatural punishment.

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: The principal ethnographic authorities (Cooper and Flannery, 1957; Flannery, 1953) describe the Supreme Being as the ultimate ruler and controller of all other supernatural beings, humans, and the Earth. This is further emphasized by the fact that the Supreme Being is the only supernatural being clearly and directly associated with supernatural punishment.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: "Sometimes supernaturally caused ailments followed automatically from the breach of taboos, others were inflicted intentionally by non-human or by human agents" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:310).

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more information on explanations for supernatural punishment.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: "Sometimes supernaturally caused ailments followed automatically from the breach of taboos, others were inflicted intentionally by non-human or by human agents" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:310). "Equally active was his [the Supreme Being's] interest in man's moral and social behavior. He was pleased at such moral or social acts as respect and help to the aged and care of the orphans, and was offended by grave breaches of the moral or social order. He bestowed reward and punishment for such human behavior exclusively or almost exclusively in this life. At death the souls of all except murderers went to the same spirit habitat, not to the Supreme Being" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:7-8).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: "He [The Supreme Being] bestowed reward and punishment for such human behavior exclusively or almost exclusively in this life. At death the souls of all except murderers went to the same spirit habitat, not to the Supreme Being" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:7-8).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: "Equally active was his [the Supreme Being's] interest in man's moral and social behavior. He was pleased at such moral or social acts as respect and help to the aged and care of the orphans, and was offended by grave breaches of the moral or social order. He bestowed reward and punishment for such human behavior exclusively or almost exclusively in this life. At death the souls of all except murderers went to the same spirit habitat, not to the Supreme Being" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:7-8). Although the Supreme Being is described as meting out punishment in this lifetime, there are limited ethnographic examples of specific punishments.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: "If he [the person elected to be keeper of the Flat Pipe] did not accept, there was no legal punishment inflicted such as physical violence, killing or banishment, but rather a supernatural one. It was thought that some grave evil would befall the person chosen if he did not accept the office" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:37).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Notes: Although the Supreme Being is said to bestow rewards (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:7-8), there are no clear ethnographic examples or further details.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of an eschatology.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: "Feasting daily during the four-day dances was customary, except during the Sacrifice Dance which entailed much fasting on the part of the participants" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:182).

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: The keeper and co-keeper of the Flat Pipe were required to follow certain food taboos (see Cooper and Flannery, 1957:65).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: The Sacrifice Dance involves a self-torture rite, but participation in this dance is not mandatory. (See Cooper and Flannery, 1957:193).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic descriptions of the Gros Ventre participating in regular meetings, services, or prayer. Religious observances seem to occur either during communal ceremonies, or as the individual desires.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Small-scale rituals are present, but it does not appear that participation is mandatory (see Cooper and Flannery, 1957:364).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: "If the bands happened to be scattered at the time a sacred Dance was to be held, runners were sent by the vower to bid them foregather for the Dance. All members of the tribe were obliged to attend the Sacrifice and Crazy Dances, and pretty surely the Drum, Kit-fox and Dog Dances. As regards the Fly Dance, this was ordinarily held in connection with one of the other Dances, so everybody would be present anyhow. As regards the Old Men's and Old Women's Dances, they were not so lively or colorful, and were held a little apart and the people did not take much interest in them and “did not go much” to them; attendance was apparently not required" (Cooper and Flannery, 1957:180).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: The Gros Ventre were traditionally comprised of about 12 bands, each led by a respective chief. Each band possessed a Flat Pipe and a Feathered Pipe Keeper, both of whom acted as religious leaders with political influence. The bands would come together as a tribal unit, which was led by a tribal chief. "The term 'chief' was employed to designate any man who had distinguished himself in war. Each band then might have several or many such 'chiefs,' but among them would be one recognized as leader, 'he who takes us around,' that is, the one who directed the band when it moved from place to place. This function seems to have been the primary one of the leader" (Flannery, 1953:31). "...Gros Ventres had had in the fairly remote past a formally selected chief or leader of the whole tribe. It was said that he functioned when the whole tribe was together and that his decisions in important matters were made in consultation with the chief men, including the leaders of all the

bands. There was no regular council and anyone present might express his opinion. Often the Keepers of the Sacred Pipes were present at such meetings called by the tribal chief, but if they were not present they were supposed to be kept advised" (Flannery, 1953: 24). Note that this "tribal chief" appears to be more of a temporary position, functioning when the bands came together. Because of this, the Gros Ventre have a less formal tribal structure. "In spite of the fact that a tribal chief was recognized, band autonomy was apparently preserved. The ceremonial organization cut across band organization, however, and band autonomy was relinquished at the times during which the Sacred Dances were held. The movements and activities of the tribe as a whole were then in the hands of the company to which the vower of a particular Dance belonged" (Flannery, 1953:36). SCCS Variable 237 (note: equivalent to EA column 33) Jurisdictional Hierarchy Beyond the Local Community indicates that the Gros Ventre have one level of political authority beyond the local community, which is indicative of a chiefdom (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004)."The society is theoretically subject to another society with an alien culture, e.g., to a colonial power, but is in fact essentially unadministered by the latter and thus enjoys de facto autonomy" (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; Column 1: Political Autonomy).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic evidence.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: "The society is theoretically subject to another society with an alien culture, e.g., to a colonial power, but is in fact essentially unadministered by the latter and thus enjoys de facto autonomy" (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; Column 1: Political Autonomy).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: SCCS variable 14, Routes of Land Transport, indicates that unimproved trails are present (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Presumably, transportation infrastructure is not present.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: "There is only incipient specialization, as when groups with other functions are assigned police functions in emergencies, e.g., military societies at a Plains Indian annual sun dance and buffalo hunt" (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; Column 10: Police).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: "Supreme judicial authority is lacking at any level above that of the local community" (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; Column 9: Judiciary).

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of institutionalized punishment.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a formal legal code.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Gros Ventre are hunter-gatherers, relying primarily on hunting, with gathering providing a secondary source of subsistence. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

Notes: The Gros Ventre are hunter-gatherers, relying primarily on hunting, with gathering providing a secondary source of subsistence. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.